

**USE AND DEVELOPMENT OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE
EDUCATIONAL PROCESS**

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Abstract: The role and importance of digital technology in ensuring the quality of higher education is listed in the article. Factors that have a positive effect on the quality and efficiency of education are analyzed. The analysis of the unique aspects of the use of traditional and digital pedagogy in the educational process is described. The problems of creating a digital educational environment are considered.

Key words: Digitization of education, digital educational environment, digital educational content, electronic educational resources, distance education technologies.

Today, the main trend in the field of education is related to the digital revolution, which leads to fundamental changes in the labor market, the emergence of new competencies, improved cooperation, responsibility of citizens, and the ability to make independent decisions. This, in turn, is a reason for further reorganization of the educational process. The development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan implies an active position of the educational community in the development of new approaches to the implementation of the educational process in the context of the digitization of professional education. Digital technologies, social networks and messengers have changed social values and led the individual to network identification. A new type of students who independently determine their educational direction has appeared. They are encouraged for personal development and self-determination, ready and able to combine studies with work. In order to solve the problems of digitization, education must go through a digital transformation. According to scientists, the digital transformation of education is the answer to global information problems in the world.

According to research, the digital transformation of education should be accompanied by a “synergistic” update of content, which will lead to a radical improvement in the quality of education. If the educational system meets the requirements and opportunities of the digital society, the digital transformation of education will lead the society to the digital economy. In the digital space, traditional pedagogical theories fall into completely new conditions. A new

digital pedagogy is forming, "the function of the teacher is fundamentally changing. It is clear that the development, experience and creation of new working models of the organization of the educational process, new mechanisms for evaluating knowledge, skills and competences, all levels of education o It is necessary to deepen the relationship between students of educational institutions and employers, to create new mechanisms for evaluating skills, to create an effective continuous education system that ensures a real transition from lifelong learning to lifelong learning.

The current stage of digitization of education is to integrate all its subjects into the digital educational environment [1].

In the digital environment, the student's activity becomes an educational unit focused primarily on concrete production actions with the information offered by the teacher or in the process of searching, selecting and interpreting it. For example, an activity can be watching a video or listening to audio, working with a built-in model, practicing skills in a virtual simulator, performing interactive tasks, or self-monitoring. Carrying out the activity - listening to the end, reading or watching and completing the task, working with a simulator, model, finding the right answers in the test, etc. The digital educational environment implies a different architecture of the educational process.

Educational content can be delivered through a variety of interconnected devices and platforms. For example, a student can receive an assignment in the distance education system, discuss it with the teacher and classmates in a social network group, ask a question to the teacher via messenger or e-mail, and prepare for the exam in the application. Thus, the digital learning environment ensures the adaptation of the individual learning trajectory, allowing each student to choose his own learning trajectory consisting of the activities needed here and now. In this regard, the environment must constantly analyze the needs and abilities of the student and offer scenarios for further development.

As part of the creation of a modern and safe digital educational environment, the following should be noted among the main tasks that every educational organization must solve: introducing a target model of the digital educational environment, updating the information content and functionality. Including training of teachers in the field of open and popular, modern online educational technologies;

- to ensure the introduction of modern digital technologies to basic educational programs and additional educational programs.

There are several definitions of “digital learning environment”. Many authors have proposed that digital learning environments (DLE) are designed to support various tasks of the educational process. It implements educational programs using electronic education and distance education technologies in the conditions of the functioning of the electronic information-educational environment. According to this document, the digital educational environment includes electronic information-educational resources, a complex of information and telecommunication technologies, and appropriate technical tools that ensure the development of educational programs by students, regardless of their location includes [2].

According to the proven objective model of the digital learning environment, the purpose of DLE is to provide equal access to the information systems and resources of the DLE platform to the participants of the educational process, suppliers and consumers of digital educational content, which is a support for improvement will give. Quality of knowledge, training, exchange of experience and practitioners, management of own information in electronic form, provision and implementation of public services in the field of education, creation of an individual curriculum, training and education is to organize the monitoring of the development of educational programs. Digitization for a professional education organization is inextricably linked with the wide use of distance learning technologies in the practice of training middle-level specialists. By distance education technologies, we mainly understand educational technologies that are implemented using information and telecommunication networks in the indirect (distance) interaction of students and teachers [3].

In conclusion, with the active use of digital skills in the educational process, the general goals of education are more successfully achieved, it is easier to develop competences in the field of communication: the ability to collect facts, compare them, organize them, express one's thoughts, discover new things, make choices and make decisions.

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